

1 **EDA2R is a marker of kidney function and a transcriptional correlate of kidney damage.**

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7 We study morbidity and mortality in humans. Chronic kidney disease is among the ten leading causes of
8 death in humans in the United States. We measured total transcription in the kidney in humans with
9 chronic kidney disease and in healthy control individuals, comparing tissue gene expression based on
10 kidney function (eGFR) to discover genes associated with kidney disease in humans. We report here the
11 discovery of EDA2R as a marker of kidney function and a transcriptional correlate of kidney damage in
12 humans.

13 Citations

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